

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Octanuclear Oxomolybdate Salts containing Aluminium and Tungsten as the Heteroatoms

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Heteropoly oxoanions containing two addenda atoms¹ of two different elements have been reported², but their three-dimensional X-ray structure elucidation have not been made so far for all such anions³. Baker and co-workers⁴ reported a few triheteropoly tungstate anions of the type $[XZW_{11}O_{40}H_n]^{Y-}$, where X = Si, Ge, P; and Z = Co^{II}, Co^{III}, Ni^{II} etc. In the present communication we report the preparations of a few salts of a new triheteropoly oxoanion $[AlWMo_8O_{32}]^{7-}$ and their characterisation by chemical analysis, thermogravimetric studies, electronic and ir spectroscopy and preliminary X-ray diffraction analysis.

Sodium, potassium and guanidinium salts of 8-molybdo-1-tungstoaluminate(III), namely $Na_7[AlWMo_8O_{32}]11H_2O$, $K_7[AlWMo_8O_{32}]14H_2O$ and $[C(NH_2)_3]_7[AlWMo_8O_{32}]18H_2O$ have been prepared at a pH range 3.2–3.6. The formulation of the compounds were made on the basis of the well established heteropoly anion $[X^{n+}Mo_9O_{32}]^{-(10-n)}$ as suggested by Waugh *et al.*⁵. The compounds were further confirmed by metathetical reactions and spectroscopic evidences.

The sharp and medium ir peaks of the compounds at 875–915 and 730–765 cm^{-1} correspond to Mo–O–Mo and Mo–O linkage respectively^{6,7}, and that at 410–440 cm^{-1} to octahedral Al–O linkage in the central cavity⁸. Antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretching mode⁶ of the peripheral water molecule is observed at 3 385–3 495 cm^{-1} . The peaks at 1 590–1 680 cm^{-1} correspond to H–O–H bending mode of water whereas those in the lower frequency region 540–580 cm^{-1} are due to lattice water owing to O–H liberational mode⁹. The high value of absorption peaks at 1 145–1 168 cm^{-1} is due to W–O, found in various heteropoly tungstates^{7,9}, which is a characteristic feature of all poly-

tungstates^{10,11}. The aqueous solution of sodium salt of $[AlWMo_8O_{32}]^{7-}$ anion was examined spectrophotometrically in various buffer solutions. It appeared to be most stable at pH 3.3. The intense broad band at approximately $4.1 \times 10^{-3} cm^{-1}$ (5.1×10^4) in the uv-region is ascribed to charge transfer^{11,12} from oxygen to tungsten. The anions are extremely inert towards analytical reducing agents and we could not determine accurately the oxidation state of the hetero atoms.

The thermal stability of the compounds were confirmed by DTA and TG analysis taking each compound (20 mg) and performing the experiment at a heating rate of 10 K min^{-1} . DTA and TG analysis showed characteristic endothermic peaks in the range 70–210 $\pm 10^\circ$ corresponding to loss of peripheral water or water of crystallisation whereas exothermic peaks in the region 280–310 $\pm 10^\circ$ indicated the loss of water of constitution of compounds. A constant plateau followed by a few weak exotherms in the TG curves above 310–450 $\pm 10^\circ$, may be due to the decomposition of the heteropoly anionic cage to the lower oxides of the metals like MoO_3 , WO_3 , Al_2O_3 etc. and their slow volatilisation¹². The physical change in colour of compound, the complete insolubility of the heated samples, the chemical analysis of the residuals and the ir spectra of the ignited samples at this region further confirmed the decomposition of the heteropoly anionic cage^{8,9}.

Fine needle-shaped single crystal for the potassium salt of the compound $K_7[AlWMo_8O_{32}]14H_2O$ was isolated and the X-ray diffraction pattern indicated it to be of hexagonal system with $a = b = 10.81$, $c = 10.21$ Å, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 120^\circ$, volume per unit cell, $v = 4885.4$ Å³; number of unit cell contained, $\tau = 4$; ob-

served density $\rho_{\text{obs}} = 1.73 \text{ g l}^{-1}$; observed molecular weight, $M = 2008$ (calcd. 2016).

Experimental

All compounds used were of AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared with distilled water. The metals were estimated using ARL 3410 atomic emission spectrophotometer, and C, H, N using Coleman analyser. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, the thermal data on a NETZSCH STA 409 analyser and X-ray diffraction data on a UNICAM instrument.

Sodium 8-molybdotungstoaluminate(III) : Aqueous solution (50 ml) containing aluminium sulphate (0.34 g) was mixed with lukewarm aqueous solution (50 ml) containing sodium tungstate (0.34 g) with constant stirring. This mixture was thoroughly mixed with aqueous solution (100 ml) containing sodium molybdate (2 g) and heated gently on a water-bath. pH of the solution was maintained at 3.2 by acetate buffer. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then evaporated to crystallisation on a water-bath and left undisturbed. Large prismatic glassy crystals appeared after 2 days which grew bigger in size and after 4 days the product was filtered, washed with ethanol (Found : Na, 8.55; Al, 1.32; W, 9.25; Mo, 41.28. $\text{Na}_7[\text{AlWMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]\cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : Na, 8.7; Al, 1.45; W, 9.94; Mo, 40.97%). The molecular formula was assigned following the views of Waugh *et al.*⁵ as $[\text{MnMo}_9\text{O}_{32}]^6$

Potassium and guanidinium salts of 8-molybdo-1-tungstoaluminate : The compounds were prepared by reacting stoichiometric amounts of the concentrated aqueous solutions of 8-molybdo-1-tungstoaluminate with that of potassium chloride and of guanidinium chloride. The resulting compounds were crystallised and analysed as discussed earlier (Found : K, 13.21; Al, 1.29; W, 9.25; Mo, 37.55. $\text{K}_7[\text{AlWMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]\cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : K, 13.57; Al, 1.33; W, 9.11; Mo, 38%); (Found : C, 3.62; N, 12.95; Al, 1.16; W, 7.95; Mo, 34.3. $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_7[\text{AlWMo}_8\text{O}_{32}]\cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : C, 3.75; N, 13.15; Al, 1.20; W, 8.22; Mo, 34.08%).

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